

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF ELECTROMAGNETIC CLUTCH SLIPPING IN WIND POWER PLANT

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Abstract

Disharding and increase of non-renewable sources of energy are forced humanity to paid attention to renewable sources of energy that one of their is wind. According to the potential possibility wind-power engineering can take second place after the hydroelectric engineering. However utilization of energy of wind is concerned with the great difficulties of technical characteristics. General questions about the utilization of energy of wind have enough highlights, however getting of quality electroenergy from wind has not adequately explored yet. In this article is discussed question about the perspective using of electromagnetic clutch slipping by way of one of elements that made better the work of wind power plant (wind-electric set).

Keywords: renewable sources, wind power plant, electromagnetic clutch slipping, frequency.

Introduction

Under the changes of speed of wind power plant is the conductor with the rapid starting and stop. For prevention of breakage and damages and also elastically junction of generator with the wind power plant, electromagnetic clutch slipping is the effective remedy. In proposal system of wind power plant, electromagnetic clutch slipping not only is execute function as turning on and disconnection of generator and also can decrement vibration of wind wheel. Electromagnetic clutch slipping that has been established between the reduction gears and electrically generator is stabilized frequency rotation at the entry of muff under the variable frequency of wind wheel and also allow to rapid junction and segregation of rollers till and during the driving work and smooth out hits from the wind wheel to the generator. As distinct from other electrically machines in electromagnetic clutch slipping at that condition for cooling is not become worst and overall dimensions of muff in this connection are not increase [1-3].

Main part

In the same way application of electromagnetic clutch slipping in wind power plant is set up the possibility under the solving of more questions about dynamics of wind power plant. As a result of this mathematical modelling and investigation of transitional process in wind wheel system — electromagnetic clutch slipping - generator is gain actual in importance. Specifically peculiarities of work as such system is contain that electromagnetic moment of muff is the compound function of slipping and current excitation. Under the consideration electromagnetic clutch slipping as an object with the distribution parameters in this situation is meet with the serious difficulties. In that case when the investigation of internal process in electromagnetic clutch slipping are not request, for the solution of task is enough take into consideration only resulting influence massive magnetic path and consideration of electromagnetic clutch slipping as an object with the fixed parameters [4-7].

In these situations for the investigation of offered systems can be used equalization of Park in a system coordinate d, q, o . System of differential equalization for the commonly known synchronous generator. For the equivalent of electromagnetic clutch slipping with the massive magnetic path is used from structural diagram setting in figure 1. Here massive inductor is equivalent under the longitudinal axis with the circuits' f and D , but massive rotor on the longitudinal axis with the circuits' d and transversal axis with the circuits' q . Possibility of such equivalence has been mentioned in (1), but in such situations can be limited with the two-three circuits for the solution of engineering task. Structural diagram has been composed on the basis of similarity of electromagnetic clutch slipping with the synchronous machines. Parameters of circuits' d and q at that is the function of current excitation and comparative rapid between the armature and inductor. Differential equations of electromagnetic clutch slipping in operator form has the aspect:

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= r_a i_d + P\psi_d - \omega_M \psi_q \\
 0 &= r_q i_q + P\psi_q - \omega_M \psi_d \\
 0 &= r_D i_D + P\psi_D \\
 U_f &= r_f i_f + P\psi_f \\
 0 &= r_Q i_Q + P\psi_Q \\
 \psi_f &= X_f i_f + X_{ad} i_d + X_{aa} i_a \\
 \psi_D &= X_D i_D + X_{ad} i_f + X_{ad} i_d \\
 \psi_Q &= X_Q i_Q + X_{aq} i_q \\
 \psi_d &= X_d i_d + X_{ad} i_D + X_{ad} i_f \\
 \psi_q &= X_q i_q + X_{aq} i_Q
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here the designation is the generally accepted. Solve system of equation (1) under $\omega_M = \text{const}$ can learn electromagnetic transitional process. Such as particular interest is present dynamics drive with the muffs to the system (1), it is necessary to add equation of movement of electric drive for the learning of electro-mechanical process [8-12].

Figure 1. Structure chart electromagnetic clutch slipping

Electromagnetic moment of muff in a system coordinate d , q , o have the aspect:

$$M_M = \psi_q i_d - \psi_d i_q \quad (2)$$

Equalization movement of clutch in general situation is described:

$$T_j P \omega_{BD} = M_{BD} - M_M \quad (3)$$

Where T_j - electromechanical time constant of wind-powered, including multiplicator and inductor of electromagnetic clutch;

ω_{BD} - rotation of wind powered; M_{BD} - torque of wind powered;

M_M - electromagnetic moment of clutch.

Rotation frequency of armature of clutch is determined as:

$$\omega_r = \omega_{BD} - \omega_M \quad (4)$$

Where ω_M - relative slip of clutch, moreover ω_{BD} , ω_r and ω_M - relative values.

Preliminary analysis of the present task displayed that under its solution is appear difficulties, connected with the necessarily of determination of parameters of electromagnetic clutch slipping, especially because during the application of electromagnetic clutch slipping with the massive magnetic path the parameters are change within the wide limits and task executable under the application only equivalent means of parameters.

Conclusions

1. Under the investigation transfer process in wind power plant contents electromagnetic clutch slipping with the massive magnetic path is arise definite difficulties with the definition parameters of muff.

2. This task is easy enough fulfillment under the utilization as called equivalent parameters of electromagnetic clutch slipping.

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